

ELIXIR Commissioned Service
2024-TECHNOLOGY-TRAINING PLATFORM
Work Package 1 - Governance of the Training Platform

M1.1 Annual Platform meeting

Tier: Technology

Executive Summary

This TrP milestone report links to the published Annual Platform Meeting report.

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Report

The 2024 ELIXIR Training Platform hybrid meeting was hosted in Prague, Czech Republic from March 4-5 2024. A full report has been published on Zenodo and can be found [here](#).

Dissemination Plans

Publishing the report on Zenodo makes it citable as a digital object.